

1 Article

2 Design and Evaluation of a Computer-Aided Diagnostic Sys- 3 tem for Chest Disease Detection Using Deep Learning-Based X- 4 ray Image Analysis

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11 2543@diu.edu.bd](mailto:antu35-2543@diu.edu.bd); momin.swe@gmail.com12 * Correspondence: ruhi.diu@gmail.com13 **Abstract**

14 Computer-aided diagnostic (CAD) systems based on chest X-ray imaging play an im-
15 portant role in supporting clinical decision-making; however, their effectiveness depends
16 not only on classification accuracy but also on robust system-level design and integration
17 within clinical workflows. This paper presents the engineering design and evaluation of
18 a deep learning-based computer-aided diagnostic system for automated detection of
19 chest diseases from X-ray images. The proposed system is architected as a modular diag-
20 nostic pipeline, incorporating image acquisition, automated preprocessing, feature extrac-
21 tion using pre-trained convolutional neural networks, and multi-class disease classifica-
22 tion. Design decisions were guided by engineering constraints such as computational ef-
23 ficiency, scalability, and clinical usability. The comparisons between the performance of
24 several pre-trained models (ResNet50, DenseNet121, InceptionV3, and MobileNetV2) un-
25 der the same system architecture were performed to study the trade-offs in the perfor-
26 mance. The evidence of experiments shows that the created CAD system has a high diag-
27 nostic accuracy and reliability and has a practical and deployable structure. In addition to
28 performance indicators, the paper provides an engineering design framework of applying
29 deep learning models to clinical decision-supporting systems, emphasizing the im-
30 portance of the system architecture and design decisions in medical image-based diagno-
31 sis.

32 **Keywords:** design; computer-aided diagnosis; chest X-ray; transfer learning; deep learn-
33 ing; ResNet50;DenseNet121; MobileNetV2; InceptionV3

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40 conditions of the [Creative Commons](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)[Attribution \(CC BY\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) license.35 **1. Introduction**

36 Pulmonary infiltrates, atelectasis, and pleural effusion are lung diseases, the symp-
37 toms of which are still considered significant health-related problems and causes of death
in the world [1]. Atelectasis is generally caused by obstruction or external compression of
lung tissue by bronchi, pleural effusion is often linked to pneumonia, pulmonary embo-
lism, malignancy, and congestive heart failure [2,3]. Pulmonary infiltrates can be caused

41 by infection, pulmonary edema, malignancy, autoimmune diseases, drug reactions, aller-
42 gic, pulmonary hemorrhage or interstitial lung diseases [4]. Clinical management can thus
43 effectively be applied with proper diagnosis that is accurate and timely.

44 The chest disease screening method which is commonly used is the Chest X-ray
45 (CXR) imaging because it is low cost, accessible and fast to acquire [5]. Nevertheless, in-
46 terpretation of CXR is usually problematic due to overlapping of anatomy, the subtle
47 pathological presentation and interobserver variability. To overcome these difficulties,
48 computer-aided diagnosis (CAD) systems have been created to assist clinicians with sta-
49 ble and objective decision-assistance products [5]. Surveys and systematic reviews have
50 found that CAD systems based on artificial intelligence can be of high diagnostic sensitiv-
51 ity and decrease radiologist workload and enhance efficiency in triage in mass-level
52 screening programs [1114]. However, inconsistency in documented performance between
53 imaging states and clinical settings point to the significance of strong and well-developed
54 CAD systems.

55 Regarding engineering design, a good CAD system will combine image acquisition,
56 automated preprocessing, feature extraction, model inference and clinician facing outputs
57 into a deployable and reliable workflow. Deep learning (DL) has shown good results in
58 medical image analysis tasks, such as classification, detection, and segmentation and has
59 generally performed better than traditional machine learning methods [6]. An important
60 design obstacle of CXR-based CAD systems is that CXR images are stored as single-chan-
61 nel grayscale images, despite the high-performing convolutional neural networks (CNNs)
62 being trained on large three-channel RGB images [7,8]. Even though grayscale images can
63 be reproduced across channels [9], this screening does not add any new information and
64 can become weak when the system-level designing considerations are not considered.

65 Transfer learning (TL) thus emerges as a popular solution when designing the CAD
66 system as it allows CNNs that have been trained with large RGB datasets to be transferred
67 to analyze CXRs [10]. The majority of current CAD systems use already trained backbones
68 like ResNet, DenseNet, MobileNet, EfficientNet, and Inception architectures because of
69 their impressive features representation and lower training data demands [16,17]. In order
70 to deal with the issues of class imbalance and overlapping radiographic patterns, a num-
71 ber of studies have suggested the concept of attention, multi-task learning models, and
72 dynamic task-weighting methods [18,19]. Although such approaches can commonly en-
73 hance the classification performance, they can often deal with the optimization of the al-
74 gorithm and do not systematically address the design choice on the architecture level,
75 computational efficiency, or deploy ability.

76 The most recent studies have been moving towards characterizing CAD as a system-
77 based clinical intervention as opposed to a stand-alone classifier. The AI-assisted triage
78 and screening systems were demonstrated to aid in the case prioritization, facilitate the
79 diagnostic processes, and assist clinical judgment without raising the diagnostic error
80 [15,20]. Many studies have revealed the usefulness of DL-based CAD systems to classify
81 chest diseases based on CXR images with high accuracy being reported trustworthy across
82 a variety of datasets and model architectures [2131]. Regardless of these developments,
83 there has been limited comparative engineering-based analyses of deep learning back-
84 bones in an integrated CAD system, in terms of modularity, efficiency, robustness, and
85 clinical implementation.

86 The engineering design in this study is considered a CAD development based on a
87 chest X-ray. A multi-class atelectasis, pleural effusion, and pulmonary infiltrates transfer
88 learning on pre-trained CNN backbones, use of ResNet50, DenseNet121, MobileNetV2,
89 and InceptionV3 is a system designed and evaluated as an end-to-end computer-aided
90 diagnostic system. The choice of these architectures is to permit a systematic comparison
91 across the various accuracy, capacity and computational efficiency profiles. The proposed

system avoids manual feature engineering and processes preprocessed CXR images directly through deep learning models, with performance assessed using standard diagnostic metrics such as accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, and precision.

The main contributions of this study are as follows:

- Design of an end-to-end CAD system integrating automated preprocessing, transfer-learning-based feature extraction, and multi-class classification for chest disease diagnosis.
- Comparative evaluation of multiple pre-trained CNN backbones within a unified system architecture to analyze performance and efficiency trade-offs.
- Deployment-oriented assessment using standard diagnostic metrics to support clinical decision-making.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the dataset, system design, and evaluation methodology. Section 3 presents the experimental results and discussion. Section 4 concludes the paper and outlines limitations and future research directions.

2. Materials and Methods

The remarkable computer vision performance of the ResNet50, DenseNet121, MobileNetV2, and InceptionNetV2 architectures piques our experimental interest. The created models and architectures are computationally fault-robust, readily marketable, and implementable as utilities. For the diagnostic tools that can assist with inexpensive image capturing and direct categorization. Therefore, this research focuses on constructing precise, trustworthy, and accurate multi-class image classification models to correctly categorize illnesses such as atelectasis, effusion, and infiltrates. This thesis looks at CXR pictures from the 5606 medical photos of individuals between the ages of 55 and 79 that are part of the National Institutes of Health (NIH) collection in the United States [5]. For our implementation purpose, we have used the dataset that has 5606 photos which include all 14 types of diseases, and representative images are present in Figure 1 [5]. In Figure 1, all sub-images include horizontal and vertical axes representing pixel positions from 0 to 1000.

Figure 1. Sample images of the dataset (Horizontal and vertical axes show pixel positions 0 -1000)

As the NIH chest X-ray (CXR) images are already at 1024×1024 resolution (which is already square), we simply removed the lower (abdominal) part to eliminate non-informative data and to standardize the field of view. Resizing of the images to 256×256 was done. We then used a center crop to 128×128 (i.e. 87.5% crop). Since the chosen CNN

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backbones use three channels as inputs, every grayscale image was copied to three channels, and it has the values of $128 \times 128 \times 3$. In order to increase the diversity of the effective sample and enhance resistance to real-life variation (e.g., position, orientation, and brightness), we used RandAugment during training [38]. The data set was divided into training, validation and test sets with 3931, 1006 and 669 images, respectively. Figure 2 is a summary of the entire CAD workflow and clinical decision-support process.

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Figure 2. Engineering architecture and clinical workflow of the proposed computer-aided diagnosis (CAD) system for chest X-ray (CXR) decision support. The workflow includes image ingestion (e.g., PACS/upload), automated preprocessing, transfer-learning-based inference, and a human-in-the-loop clinician review stage leading to reporting and follow-up actions.

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The suggested CAD system is modeled as a pipeline with few highly standardized modules whereby the image ingestion module leads to the standardized preprocessing, transfer-learning-based inference, and decision support that the clinician can access (Figures 23). Its design focuses on: (i) the standardization of inputs to enhance robustness, (ii) backbone selection that can automatically be exchanged to explore the performance-efficiency trade-offs and (iii) confidence-aware outputs to support human-in-the-loop clinical review, as opposed to substituting clinical judgment.

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The proposed paper compares four pre-trained CNN backbones, ResNet50, DenseNet121, MobileNetV2, and InceptionV3, and the ImageNet pre-trained weights. Applying pre-trained models can be useful in case of a comparatively small dataset since it will save time on training and computational expenses, and it will be taking advantage of transferable visual characteristics. ResNet50 and DenseNet121 can represent finer details with deeper representations; MobileNetV2 can be used on computers with limited resources; and InceptionV3 with multi-scale feature extraction using parallel convolutional paths.

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ResNet50 [32] takes as inputs the shape $(128, 128, 3)$, and employs residual connections in an attempt to promote deep feature-learning. DenseNet121 [33] employs a dense connection among layers to stimulate feature-reuse and enhance flow of gradients. MobileNetV2 [34] is the architecture that is constructed on depth wise separable convolutions on top of inverted residual blocks to minimize computation. InceptionV3 [35] uses Inception modules which use parallel filters of various scales and pooling to identify multi-scale features. The same classification head was applied in all backbones (Global Average

Pooling 3-class fully connected layer SoftMax). Figure 3 shows the modular design of the pipeline.

A two-stage fine-tuning approach was used to train four foundation models (ResNet50, DenseNet121, MobileNetV2 and InceptionV3). The dropout (rate = 0.2) was used to regularize the model to minimize overfitting. Lookahead was used in the optimization with Rectified Adam and clip norm = 1 to ensure the stability of the training. There was warm-up fraction of 0.1 and the learning rate was varied between the two training phases. The loss was categorical cross-entropy, and the label smoothing was set to 0.1, and SoftMax as the last classifier. The batch size was 16 to make a trade-off between the training stability and the computational efficiency.

Figure 3. Modular CAD pipeline from CXR preprocessing to multi-class prediction. Inputs are standardized through preprocessing; augmentation is applied during training for robustness. Interchangeable pre-trained CNN backbones are followed by a classification head (GAP + FC + SoftMax) that outputs class probabilities, predicted label, and confidence score.

The whole study was conducted using a personal computer equipped with an Intel Core i7-9940X 3.30 GHz CPU, 64 GB of RAM, and a NVidia GeForce RTX 3090 GPU (1755 MHz, 10,496 cores, 24 GB). Python 3.9 and Tensor Flow 2.8 were used to write the code. To evaluate the performance of the used models and find the most optimal for disease classification, evaluation metrics such as accuracy, ROC, precision, and recall were used in this study [36] [37]. These metrics were calculated using the true positive, true negative, false positive, and false negative values.

3. Results

This section may be divided by subheadings. It should provide a concise and precise description of the experimental results, their interpretation, as well as the experimental conclusions that can be drawn.

An in-depth analysis is carried out in this study to evaluate the performance of four pre-trained models in classifying chest x-ray images. Tables 1 and 2 present a comprehensive comparison of the four models' performance on both training and validation data. The outcome suggested that ResNet50 outperformed other models. It was discovered that the MobileNetV2 model was underfitting during the training dataset. This architecture has less capacity to handle the complexity of image data, and it also needs more epochs than other models. However, the other three models showed their best performance in this study with 5 epochs. The evaluation includes essential measures such as accuracy, precision, recall, AUC and loss for both the training and validation datasets are presented in Figure 4, Figure 5 and Figure 6, respectively. Moreover, the address model illustrates a satisfactory generalization ability in the evaluation process conducted in this study; its average test inference time was 0.2 second. The fast inference time is highly crucial for clinical decision-making applications in model deployment. The results presented in Tables 1 and 2 strongly exhibit that the generalization capabilities of the ResNet50 model are higher than three other models. Also, its performance, which was measured by different

performance metrics, is highly consistent in both the training and validation sets. The training and validation accuracy of ResNet50 was very close, which illustrated that there is no notable overfitting issue.

Table 1. The performance of models in the training set

Model	Loss	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	AUC
DenseNet121	1.67	96.00	95.75	59.41	89.87
MobileNetV2	3.70	61.00	65.57	42.28	71.70
Inception-NetV3	1.93	91.00	94.50	63.01	88.68
ResNet50	0.23	98.00	98.64	71.06	87.03

Table 2. The performance of models in the validation set

Model	Loss	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	AUC
DenseNet121	1.70	96.00	98.59	66.06	89.13
MobileNetV2	3.50	69.00	40.76	28.14	68.00
InceptionNetV3	1.80	91.55	96.43	66.57	89.35
ResNet50	0.23	99.01	97.72	62.29	88.35

Table 3. Comparison of ROC AUC scores for four models across three classes.

Pathology	ResNet50	DenseNet121	MobileNetV2	InceptionNetV3
Atelectasis	52	52	50	45
Infiltration	55	46	48	48
Effusion	50	45	44	52

In Table 3, ROC AUC scores of ResNet50, DenseNet121, MobileNetV2, and InceptionNetV3 models are given, where ResNet50 outperformed other models in two classes, such as atelectasis and infiltration. In the effusion class, it acquired a lower score but was very close to the highest score. The findings showed that with the training dataset, DenseNet121 attained an accuracy of 96% with a loss of 1.67. The precision and recall for this model were 95.75% and 59.41%, respectively, suggesting a significant capacity to appropriately identify positive cases, yet there is an opportunity for improvement in recall. The AUC value of 89.87 further verifies the model's overall efficacy. In validation, the accuracy remained high at 96%, and precision greatly increased to 98.59%, while recall somewhat dropped to 66.06%. The AUC of 89.13 indicates strong ability to discriminate.

The performance of MobileV2 on the training set was worse with an accuracy of 61% and more loss of 3.7. The accuracy, recall as well as AUC were 65.57, 42.28 and 71.7 respectively. The model had a memory problem as he was not good at piling up all the positive memories. The accuracy improved to 69 in validation but the precision improved to 40.76, still low was the recall of 28.14. The AUC of 68 demonstrates slightly good discrimination ability.

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Figure 4. The performance of pre-trained models of the training set

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Figure 5. The performance of pre-trained models of the validation set

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Figure 6. The loss of pre-trained models of on the training and validation sets

InceptionNetV3 gave a good accuracy of 91% and a loss of 1.93 in the training set. The model was highly precise (94.50) and recall (63.01), which makes it balanced. This is further demonstrated in its discriminative capacity by the AUC of 88.68. During validation, the accuracy was also found to be 91.55 and the precision and recall were 96.43 and 66.57, respectively. The AUC was found to be high at 89.35 implying discriminative performance which was sustained.

ResNet50 performed very well in the training dataset and achieved a high accuracy of 98, a low loss value of 0.23 and a high precision of 98.64. The AUC and recall were 71.06 and 87.03 respectively. The model ensured that a high level of accuracy of 99.01 was achieved in validation, whereas the precision was maintained at 97.72. However, recall dropped to 62.29%. The AUC of 88.35 has good discriminating behavior but with a small decrease compared to training set.

In general, ResNet50 was very accurate and precise, and the recall can be improved. DenseNet121, InceptionNetV3, and ResNet50 suggest high overall performance although MobileNetV2 suggests potential improvement with respect to recall and precision. These validation findings suggest that the models will be useful in the real world as they can be applied to unknown data. The accuracy and loss graph of the training and validation obtained in Figure 7. Lastly, on the test set, four trained models with pre-trained ResNet50, DenseNet121, MobileNetV2, and Inception Net V3 had 98.12, 96.54, 58.67, and 91.32 accuracy. ResNet50 had a great performance in both training, validation and test sets, which also performed well in literature compared to the existing studies.

Figure 7. RestNet50 model performance during training and validation process; (a) accuracy (b) loss

4. Discussion

This paper has analyzed the design and performance of a deep learning model-based computer-aided diagnosis (CAD) system of chest X-ray (CXR) image analysis, and has particularly focused on testing various pretrained convolutional neural network (CNN) backbones in a single and deployment friendly structure. The findings indicate that transfer learning is a suitable approach to CXR-based diagnosis, which allows accomplishing successful work even with limited annotated medical data. In general, it can be concluded that architectural choice is an important factor that defines diagnostic accuracy and computational efficiency.

In line with previous studies, more intricate CNN models had better classification results because of their potential to extract complicated and hierarchical image characteristics. Nevertheless, it is also demonstrated that lightweight architectures are able to deliver competitive accuracy at a substantially lower computational cost and inference pace. This brings out a critical trade-off of performance versus efficiency in the perspective of engineering design when creating CAD systems that are applicable in real clinical setting. In well-resourced environments, the high capability models might be desirable whereas in real-time applications and resource limited healthcare facilities lightweight models can be more appropriate.

One of the contributions of this work is the modular system design whereby different backbone architectures can be tested with the same preprocessing, training and evaluation conditions. This method enhances reproducibility, and allows systematic comparison of design alternatives, which is not present in work on CAD studies that mainly aim to optimize individual models. The study offers information on more than algorithmic performance and by positioning CAD development as an engineering design problem, the study can guide the practical deployment decisions.

Although these results are promising, a number of limitations are to be admitted. The study was done on one dataset and this might not be generalizable to different institutions, imaging devices, and patient groups. Besides, the system is concerned with image-level classification and lacks localization and explain ability mechanics that are gaining more and more significance in clinical acceptance and trust.

In the future, an increased emphasis should be made on multi-center validation to determine strength in different clinical settings. The explanation of AI, the ability to use the framework on multi-modal clinical data, and testing real-time deployment conditions would also make CAD systems more practical and effective in interpreting chest X-ray data.

5. Conclusions

The paper herein offered the engineering design and analysis of a computer-aided diagnostic (CAD) system to perform automated classification of chest diseases with chest X-ray images. Instead of being concerned about predictive accuracy alone, the suggested approach actually defines the development of CAD as a system-level engineering design problem, where architectural structure, modularity, and deploy ability are the key concerns. The proposed system is a combination of automated preprocessing, feature extraction through transfer learning, and multi-class classification in a coherent diagnostic workflow that can fit in a clinical setting.

Several backbones of the pre-trained convolutional neural networks, namely, ResNet50, DenseNet121, MobileNetV2, and InceptionV3, were compared under the same CAD architecture. This comparison suggests the effects of backbone choice on diagnostic performance, computational complexity, and resource demands, showing that; backbone choice is a critical design trade-off in the implementation of a practical CAD system. The findings affirm that it is possible to have reliable performance of diagnostic performance besides being flexible to modify the system design to various operational constraints.

In addition to algorithmic assessment, the work adds a modular framework of the CAD system design, which enhances reproducibility, scalability, and clinical integration. The suggested architecture allows replacing learning elements systematically and does not change the overall workflow, which is useful in the different clinical settings and deployment conditions. The system design facilitates the translation of experimental deep learning models to clinical applications in the real world by expressly considering engineering factors like robustness, efficiency and decision support-oriented outputs.

Several limitations of the present study should be acknowledged. The evaluation was restricted to a limited set of chest disease categories and a single imaging modality. Future work will focus on extending the system design to additional disease classes, multi-label classification tasks, and multi-modal data integration. Further validation in clinical environments, including human-in-the-loop assessment and workflow integration studies, will also be pursued to strengthen the system's practical applicability.

6. Patents

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, Mst. Arifa Khatun; methodology, Mst. Arifa Khatun; software, Antu Saha; validation, Mst. Arifa Khatun, Antu Saha, and MD. Momin; formal analysis, Antu Saha; investigation, Antu Saha; resources, Xiao-zhi Gao; data curation, Antu Saha; writing-original draft preparation, MD. Momin; writing-review and editing, MD. Momin and Xiao-zhi Gao; visualization, Antu Saha; supervision, Xiao-zhi Gao; project administration, Xiao-zhi Gao.

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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

AI	Artificial Intelligence
ML	Machine Learning
DL	Deep Learning
CXR	Chest X-ray
CAD	Computer-Aided Diagnostic System
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
TL	Transfer Learning
SVM	Support Vector Machine
k-NN	k-Nearest Neighbor
DT	Decision Tree
NB	Naïve Bayes
NIH	National Institutes of Health
PMD	Pre-Trained Model
ROI	Region of Interest
AUC	Area Under the Curve
NN	Neural Network
RF	Random Forest

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